

most effective against stem borer and leaffolder. Treated plants yielded 4–5 t/ha compared with 1.9–2.5 t/ha for the untreated control. It was most effective in both seasons and at both dosages. Isofenphos (0.5 kg ai/ha) and thiocy-

clam hydrogen oxalate 90 SP successfully reduced yield losses to yellow stem borer and leaffolder (see table). Carbo-sulfan, an analogue of carbofuran, was effective against stem borer and leaf-folder. Fenvalerate, a synthetic pyre-

throid, was effective against leaffolder at reproductive phase of the crop under rainy season conditions. Bendiocarb and phosalone were least effective. ✎

Seasonal incidence of rice whorl maggot at Tirur, India

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In the Chingleput district of Tamil Nadu, rice is planted continuously, depending on availability of water from lift irrigation wells. Seasonal incidence of rice whorl maggot was studied in 36 planting dates 10 days apart at Tirur PES. The first planting was 10 May 1980, the last 30 April 1981. Six varieties were evaluated without chemical protection.

Seasonal incidence of rice whorl maggot at Tirur, India, 1980-81.

Planting date	Damage mean (%)
10-5-1980	8.7
20-5	6.5
30-5	7.8
10-6	6.8
20-6	5.0
30-6	4.4
10-7	16.7
20-7	18.4
30-7	13.2
10-8	10.1
20-8	12.9
30-8	10.9
10-9	13.6
20-9	10.1
30-9	15.4
10-10	20.6
20-10	26.3
30-10	20.6
10-11	14.0
20-11	14.5
30-11	13.6
10-12	15.8
20-12	26.9
30-12	33.3
10-1-1981	32.6
20-1	27.6
30-4	17.4
10-2	18.7
20-2	10.1
2-3	11.2
11-3	12.6
21-3	11.7
31-3	11.3
10-4	14.0
20-4	10.2
30-4	14.4

CD (4.99)

Whorl maggot damage to tillers was assessed 30 days after transplanting (DT).

Whorl maggot damage was less than 10% in May-June plantings, 10–20% in July, August, September, February, March, and April plantings, and above

20% in October, December, and January plantings (see table). Pest damage was significantly less on crops planted on 20 and 30 June, and significantly higher on crops planted 20 December to 20 January. The varieties were equally susceptible. ✎

A new scarabaeid beetle pest of dry-land rice in Bangladesh

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Since 1978 a scarabaeid beetle, *Heteronychus lioderes* Redtenbacher, has

caused severe damage to dryland rice in Noakhali, Chittagong, Comilla, and Mymensingh, and on the islands of Sandwip and Hatiya.

Farmers on Sandwip Island, where the beetle is called *talkora* reported a serious outbreak of the pest during April and May 1980 in aus rice (March-August). Aman (July-December) and boro (November-June) crops have also been attacked during dry periods.

Adult beetles are black and about 16 mm long (Fig. 1). They damage plants

1. Scarabaeid beetles, genus *Heteronychus*, that have damaged dryland rice in Bangladesh.